

IFA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN ILE- IFE

Data source: Personal Expertise

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** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

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Ife is indeed a place of great cultural and religious significance among the Yoruba people in Nigeria. It holds a unique position in Yoruba history and traditions. Ife has a relatively small population of approximately 49,000 people. The Ooni of Ife, often regarded as the spiritual leader of all Yoruba people, is a figure of immense importance. The Ooni wields significant influence over both the historical and contemporary affairs of the Yoruba people. This leadership role is not just symbolic but carries practical importance in various aspects of Yoruba culture and traditions. Ife is deeply rooted in Yoruba religious traditions. The Yoruba people practice a form of traditional religion that involves the worship of various deities (orisha) and ancestral spirits. These deities play a vital role in Yoruba religious practices. Some of the prominent deities with strong connections to Ife include Oduduwa, Obatala, Yemonja, Aje, Ogun, and Ifa. Orunmila, the head of the Ifa cult, is particularly revered for his special gift of spiritual wisdom and knowledge, as well as for initiating Ifa divination, which is a central aspect of Ife religious practices. Agriculture, particularly farming, is a crucial economic activity in Ife. The Ife people rely on farming for sustenance, trade, and medicinal purposes. Agriculture not only provides food but also serves as a source of traditional medicine, underlining its importance in the community's survival and well-being. The history of Ife is primarily passed down through oral traditions. While it may not be documented in written texts like religious scriptures, these oral histories are valuable sources of information about the city's cultural and historical significance. Oral traditions are a common way of preserving history and cultural knowledge among many African societies. The two notable kings in the history of Ife are Adesoji Aderemi and Okunade Sijuwade. They made significant contributions to the development of Ife. Adesoji Aderemi, as the first indigenous governor of Western Nigeria, focused on promoting indigenous religion and cultural practices. Okunade Sijuwade continued to support social and religious activities in Ife, gaining international attention and recognition. Ife's rich cultural heritage, religious traditions, and historical importance make it a unique and vital city within Nigeria and the broader Yoruba culture. The Ifa group and the worship of Yoruba deities are integral components of the city's cultural and religious tapestry, reflecting the deep-rooted traditions and spirituality of the Ife people. This entry will therefore look at the religious tradition of the Ifa group of ife people.

Date Range: 1930 CE - 2015 CE

Region: Ile-Ife

Region tags: Nigeria, Ile-Ife

Ile-Ife is the ancestral home of the Yoruba people

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Jacob K. Olupona, (2011) *City of 201 Gods: Ile-Ife in Time, Space, and the Imagination*, California: University of California Press
- Source 2: Fabunmi M.A. (1976) *History of Ile-Ife*:Ile-Ife,Ife University Press
- Source 3: Daramola O.M.A.,(2001) *The Osirigi Drum and Ife Royalty in Odu*, O.A.U.Press, No 42

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.southernsemioticreview.net/a-socio-religious-analysis-of-indigenous-drums-in-olojo-festival-by-olusegun-oladosu/>
- Source 1 Description: This source looks at the socio-religious activities of Yoruba indigenous drums in the Olojo festival and its political value attached to the sacredness of the authority which the king wields over his subjects. The article look at the major socio-religious importance of the drum among the Ile-Ife people, and the drum's critical role in maintaining not only the integrity of the sacred performances, but also the leadership and control enjoyed by the sacred kingship within Ile - Ife society.
- Source 2 URL: <https://eujournal.org/index.php/esj/article/view/5186#:~:text=https%3A//eujournal.org/index.php/esj/article/view/5186> (Olusegun, O. (2015). YORUBA INDIGENOUS DRUMS: AN AESTHETIC SYMBOL IN ECOLOGICAL RITUAL OF THE YORUBA)
- Source 2 Description: The attempt of this paper observed and explored the connection between indigenous drum, the divinities, and the religion of the Yoruba people and its spiritual function in the environment where they exist. This work also looks at religion as a way of life for the African people. The structure of their religion identifies this in its fivefold classification which is belief in God, in divinities, in spirit, in the ancestors and in the practice of magic and medicine. Within these classifications is the element of anthropomorphism which expresses the ideas or concept about preternatural world of realities. The concept is keenly attached to the principle of animism which means beliefs in spirits that are separate and separable entities. The spirit world of African religion is initiated by the belief that certain spiritual entities reside in natural phenomena or landmarks such as rivers, mountains, or trees that serve as focus of communal ritual. The communal rituals in this regard show the attention or the preference given to the supernatural potency of a particular tree in the area of their spiritual understanding. Yoruba views about this gives the impression that all useful trees were thought to harbour gods or spirits which are venerated or worshiped in some occasions. Some of these trees are therefore considered as best material for drum making. Drums made from most of these trees are hence associated with ritual functions because they believe that the drum carries the spiritual potency of the gods or spirits of the tree which they are made from.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/i275558> (Ogun onire by Renato Berger in African Arts Journal, Vol 8,No1)
- Source 3 Description: This work shows that no culture is ever static, and indeed traditional African culture was in its own way often dynamic. This view shows that Yoruba indigenous culture and belief have a continuous way of providing landmark for the discoveries of styles and experiences for the way people live. These styles and experiences reflect the ideas and spirituality that identify the importance of Yoruba culture. Akin Euba as cited by Renato Berger in this work noted that Yoruba art and culture is not simply an art form, but combine several different bodies of knowledge including traditional medicine and science, history, law and philosophy. This is the view which this entry also identified.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: World History Encyclopedia <https://www.worldhistory.org> › Ife
- Source 1 Description: This work looks at the early civilization in Ife during the pre modern time. It also identified the cosmological stories of Ife as well as the importance of archaeology and pre modern arts

development in Ife and other places associated with them.

– Source 2 URL: http://www.metmuseum.org/toah/hd/ife/hd_ife.htm

– Source 2 Description: This field identified the significance of Ife people to the Yoruba socio-religious existence. It identified them as a traditionally urban people who represent one of the largest ethnic groups in Nigeria and on the African continent. It shows that through them, in the African diaspora, Yoruba heritage has made tremendous contributions to the cultures of countries like Cuba, Brazil, and the United States

– Source 3 URL: <https://academic-accelerator.com/encyclopedia/yoruba-religion>

– Source 3 Description: This source is about religious beliefs of the Yoruba people. It narrated the areas in which the development of their belief system sprang from. These areas include comprehensive complex of songs, histories, stories and other cultural concepts that make up Yoruba society

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Recruitment is hereditary and through family tradition.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 409000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1.9

Notes: The adherents of this religious group are predominantly from the indigenous clans of Ile-Ife. Most of the followers of the Ifa oracle share family ties.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

Notes: The traditional ruler of Ile-Ife (the Ooni of Ife) installs the Araba or leader of the Ifa religious group in a very elaborate festival/celebration.

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The religious group has an oral scriptures which has been meticulously preserved, committed to the memory of religious specialists and passed on from generations past.

↳ Are they written:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

- ↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
 - No
- ↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:
 - No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Percentage: 40
 - Notes: The largest monument in ife is oranmiyan monument which measured 40/8 inches tall and 20 feet wide
- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:
 - Square meters: 100
- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
 - Height, meters: 40
- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
 - Height, square meters: 40
- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:
 - Height, meters: 20
- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Percentage of area: 20

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– I don't know

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: There are places where animals are slaughtered, libation is poured and spirits are invoked

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: There are altars built and serviced by Ifa priests. These altars serve as devotional markers to adherents.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Shrines, grooves, sacred forest

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The Yoruba concept of afterlife is encapsulated in their worldview of the ancestral cult. In the cult of the ancestors, transmigration of the dead takes place. The dead ancestors find their solace in this realm and they also can supervise their kinsmen left here on earth. In the Yoruba worldview it is important for every dead fellow to join this cult of the ancestors. It is unimaginable for any dead person who died in a full ripe old age to be excluded from the cult. Failure to be admitted into the cult after death is a signal the fellow is being punished for wrongdoing. Although this entry is about the Ifa religious group in Yorubaland, reference is made to another indigenous religious group (cult of the ancestors) among the people because the subject of religion among Yoruba indigenous religious groups involves complementarity of ideals and practices. Among the Yoruba, one religious group could be the custodians of a practice which applies to other groups without necessarily generating conflicts or friction between the groups.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The spatial location is described through the migration of the deceased to the ancestral world known as the cult of the ancestors.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Reincarnation is a major hallmark of this religion because it shows the essence and significance of ancestors among the people. It is a means of rewarding both good and bad deeds recorded against each individual while living on earth. Reincarnation occurs when new born babies who are indeed the departed parents and grand parents are born into the same family they left a while ago.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: Reincarnation in human form within the religious tradition of Ifa devotees is a medium for departed parents to return to the world for reward or punishment. This is an eschatology adopted in Yoruba tradition.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: Those who have not done well in the world are considered to reincarnate in animal or plant form as a means of punishment.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

Notes: This is also a means of punishment for those who failed to do well in the world before their death

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Two groups of rebirth can be discerned . The most important group consists of deceased aged parents who are reborn into their families. A second group consists of children lost at infancy who return into the family as new born babies. These children are known as abiku. A corporate rebirth in this tradition is associated with the cyclical transformation of the dead from the other world back to the present world again as often as they deem fit. It identified the fact that the ancestor in this manner survived death and can still come back to be rewarded for their actions and deeds. For good deeds, such returnee will have a rebirth into the lineage where they lived.

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: This is a reward for actions exhibited in a previous life. It indicates judgement of reaping what is sowed in the previous life.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: If such is a religious leader, necessary rituals must be performed for a smooth transmigration of the soul of the leader.

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: This religious group stipulates the requirements for the rituals that will be performed on the corpse of the deceased member. The rituals could be take a few days to complete. The group also determines the items to be used for the burial.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: In the past the group practised rituals involving human sacrifice. However, this has been discontinued as a result of modernization.

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Instead of human sacrifice , animal sacrifice is now used as replacement. During the transitioning rituals for important leaders like the king and high ranking priests, there must animal sacrifice.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Special foods like palm oil, snail, and other items are provided at the grave side for important religious leaders. In most cases, family member are presented with gifts of white cloth at the grave of their kinsmen to reinforce the principle of consanguinity.

↳ Personal effects:

– No

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– No

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: There is the presentation of white clothes to the children and close relations of the deceased.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: To die a good death qualifies such deceased fellow for a place among the ancestors. This underscores the reason for organising formal burials to allow the deceased enjoy a good rest in the grave. If a fellow dies mysteriously, like drowning, falling from a tree, through some uncommon accident and diseases like smallpox, the normal burial protocols will not be followed.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: This is done for ancestors who are warriors or for itinerant religious leaders who are always on assignment. Their cenotaph will sometime be turned to shrines where their deeds and bravery are extolled. Such places also serve to connect living members of their cult or families with the venerated personality.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: There are special religious cemetery or ancestral cemetery dedicated for burial of special religious figure.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: there are family tomb for general burial

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: for special recognition of good deeds delivered during the lifetime of the decease, such individual could be interred in a domestic area in order to immortalize their name .

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In Yoruba worldview , spirit is a supernatural being, often but not exclusively a non-physical entity; such as a ghost, fairy, jinn, malevolent and benevolent being that are prevalent in different direction.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Olodumare is the supreme high God.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: omniscience, omnipresence, transcendence, provider
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Revelation is the act of God and to the understanding of the people, divine message can be obtained through the situation of things in their environment controlled by the supreme high god

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

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– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: He has knowledge of the realm of the ancestors.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Pity mercy and kindness

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Nature and environmental objects

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: There are deities who were once humans. They became deified after they died and transited this realm of existence. human spirits. They are referred to as deified deities. While they existed in human form, they heroes. Now they are highly spiritual. Examples are osun, moremi, olokun, oluorogbo

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: in the past they can be physically felt but presently they are separated from human interaction due to pollution and human errors

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: They have knowledge of this world because they are both spirit and human

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: They have divine attribute which makes them supernatural.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: They are superhuman as their ubiquitous influence can be found everywhere.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Spiritual instinct is a divine attribute possessed by superhuman being. In this religious group such heritage is embraced as a means of correction that brings orderliness into the society.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: They are agent of social control. They monitor human affairs for reward most appropriate.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: They are consulted for directions before any step is taken towards human development. They give divine advise on what will help self undertaking or bring stability to the society.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: They have this privilege because they are social agent that monitor human affairs and their relationship. Power to reward accordingly belong to them.

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: They communicate with both living and the non living because of their divine attributes.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

–Yes [specify]: They still feel sense of belonging as they are incharge of moral and ethical values of the people.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Being close to the living, they can understand the needs of the living and being an intermediary between living and the ultimate supreme they can approach God directly. They are sole umpire in spiritual activities of the adherents.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: When spirit communicate with the living through dreams, the living will then consult the priest to find out the meaning of the dream. The dreams are taken seriously as solution for whatever revelation will be given attention.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit may enter a person as medium to communicate with the living.

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: A diviner is consulted when the spirits reveals himself through dreams or trouble. The diviner is a medium who is able to communicate with spirits

Reference: Gehman, Richard . African Traditional Religion :in the Light of the Bible. Plateau: Acts, 2013.

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits in this religious group are ubiquitous. They are found everywhere like bushes, forest, rivers, and mountains. The spirits are therefore identified with natural phenomena. The

group practices a system known as diffused monotheism which is essentially the recognition of a supreme being who has left a lot of responsibility of organising the physical and spiritual aspects of the universe in the hands of smaller deities, deified ancestors and spirits.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: They cannot be seen but can be represented symbolically. Through effigy or objects, libation can be provided for them.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: They are spiritually discern to know beyond physical

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Non- human supernatural beings like spirits which inhabit natural phenomena have an expansive knowledge not accessible to humans

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: They are social agents through which human affairs can be moderated. they can reward and punish. they are greatly feared.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: They are provided with food sacrifice which tends to be spiritual. Spirit liquor is

major in this sacrifice

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They can be malevolent and as well benevolent in character. There are some that are ambivalence .

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Mixed human divine beings are those with unseen powers. Sometime such power may not have a natural description. These are the powers of witchcraft, magic and sorcery.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: They possess esoteric power that makes them have instincts of human

presence anywhere.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– Yes [specify]: They experiment esoteric power through which revelation and vision are given.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They use esoteric power to display their intent

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: A diviner acts as a medium through which the spirits of mixed human divine beings speak to the living. Dreams and visions are other ways by which mixed human - divine beings also communicate with the living.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: some of the non human spirits are domicile with kinship peculiarity because they are label with professional identity or heritage peculiarity that establish a family model.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: There is a diffused system in the pantheon of hierarchy in which a primordial and deified deity are recognized.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are social agents. When the living fail to follow the customs of the fathers, it becomes the duty of the ancestor to correct their mistakes.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Some foods items are inherently forbidden within the cult of supernatural being.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Some mountains, rivers, valleys and forests are sacred spaces. These spaces serve as spiritual monument that must not be desecrated by the profane.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Objects like iron, stone, cowry trees are examples of sacred objects. These objects are used as medium of divination for spiritual purposes.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

–Yes [specify]: They care about their affiliated religious group

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: They are against shedding innocent blood

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Religious discipline is highly admonished

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: There is need to respect the goddess of the mother earth who is in charge of oath. Anyone that contravene the ordinance of the mother earth will be punished.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

Notes: They have a free world where spiritual activities can be managed. Sorcery is an aspect of religious practice that people can engage in.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: This is a way through which the living appease the spirit to restore peace and prosperity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: There is religious freedom where you're not enforced to be dogmatic

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: They care about peaceful coexistence and sanctity of life

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: They mete out punishment to control antisocial activities. This is done to bring check and order in the society.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Since the religious structure is founded on a pluralistic pattern, this allow different supernatural beings an act to punish accordingly.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This is emphasized because their views indicates that it is the present that cater for the future. In this regard the future existence in the world would be a platform in which the eternal will be judged

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The extreme sensory displeasure explain the intention of why the privilege of reincarnation could be forfeited.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: some myth show how some reincarnated into inanimate objects like stone, tree or in some cases animal.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

Notes: The realm of the ancestor belong to those who maintained a balance and peaceful relationship while on earth but if otherwise those who are punished may go to the realm of pot shed(orun apadi)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - No

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
 - Notes: if actions and habits are against peaceful social coexistence, this may recur to natural disaster in terms of drought, flooding , lanslide which are prevalent nowadays.

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
 - Notes: Cases like motor accident or any accident attached to journey failure are always credited to punishment for wrongdoing.

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: sicknesses like smallpox, ebola, covid and lot of disease infections are always consider as punishment in this category as type of sickness or illness .

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: While they represent the divine wrath in some cases they can help people to solve their problems. They increase the traders sales , they cause abundant farm yields and they change bad destiny to good destiny.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: When they are in good tune with people through sacrifice they show attitude of kindness by rewarding their adherent.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Notes: There is a general belief that death is not the end of man. The idea of reward is shown through means of soul reincarnating and be born as a grandchild to a child of departed parents. This is a means of returning in a superior life form.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

Notes: Joining the cult of the ancestors in another realm is a superior realm consider to be a reward for good life spent.

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: The belief in the death, judgement and final resting place of the soul is not view in vertical form like that of Christianity but conceived in cyclical form. The essence of cyclical reincarnation through a reborn of child as ancestor depicts evidence of resurrections compared to that of Christianity

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are conventional moral ethics that must be followed. These are guided by stipulated rituals in some cases. Stealing is seriously abhorred. Thieves could be disgraced during festivals to dissuade others from such act.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

Notes: This was strongly emphasized in the ancient time during edi festival. But now, civilization has weaken the effect of this principle

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: They have norms concerning acceptable and unacceptable sexual relations among their members

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

– Yes

- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: During festivals or the performance of rituals, key figures or group of religious leaders may engage in fasting as part of spiritual activities.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: This is in a case when someone die by committing suicide through hanging. Such person has contradicted the natural order of the society. In that case the body and all the personal effect and properties of the decease will be confiscated for ritual to the gods. The priest that unloosed the body from the hanging point will therefore take charge of the properties.

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: To the priest within the religious group.

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: There are general meetings where indigenous religious practitioner gather to deliberate on the affairs of their faith.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: There are always private or household ritual for the initiate. Example are naming ritual or burial ritual

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 24

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: There are festivals that bring together people from different works of life.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 300

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 12

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Since sacrifice involve libations, intoxicants like schnapps are provided during the ceremony.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

↳ Circumcision:

– I don't know

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: Invocations are ritualistic utterances that must be recited at specific stages of the festival of this group.

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: This is a tribe through which the race of entire Yoruba people are described. A crucial and significant person in this race is identified to be Oduduwa. According to Yoruba beliefs, Oduduwa is considered the originator of the Yoruba people and is referred to as the first king of the Yoruba people. Oduduwa was the holder of the title Ooni of Il-Ife. He was not only the first leader of ile-ife but also the ancestor of various independent royal dynasties of Yoruba crowned kings.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There is farm settlement where native and members are allocated acres of land for their farming scheme.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: the king of the city of this religious group always provide palliative to cushion the effect of hardship for the people.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Non governmental organizations in various type do normally propel relief packaging for the people.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through NGO'S and government agencies

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: There are now indigenous educational schemes sponsored by UNESCO for primary education for children who identify with this group.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: government schools are also open for this group.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The religious groups have a good link with UNESCO on cultural ground and other developmental scheme.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Agencies like National orientation Agency (NOA), Ministries of Art and Culture are institutional bureaucracies which the group has links with.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: NGO'S and other government agencies provides this service.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through government agency like water corporation

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– I don't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Annual contributions are done for the progress of the group

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: For the production of social services, government levy taxes on every group.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are also covered by civil law. They are therefore liable to any rule of law within society.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: for capital punishment and related offences

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: If the offence is under corrupt practices, such are liable to this punishment.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subject to civil law of the government and society.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members can be coscripted into the army

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by

an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Yoruba language is native to the group

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English language is considered to be the lingua franca of the country in which the group exist.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is used in schools by their children and in official meetings by adult members.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subjected to Gregorian calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: They have native and indigenous farming scheme

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: These are major ways the people do their farming scheme in low scale level. Flowing river serves a good purpose in their system of irrigation. Most do not have access to financial assistance from the government.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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